

N-Bromosaccharin as an Oxidising Agent—A Kinetic Study Using Aliphatic and Cyclic Ketones in Aqueous Acetic Acid

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The kinetics of oxidation of aliphatic and cyclic ketones by N-bromosaccharin has been investigated in aq. acetic acid medium in the temp. range 10–50°. The reaction is found to be first order both with respect to [ketone] and [hydrogen ion] and independent of [oxidant]. The reaction is of ion-dipole type and it does not initiate polymerisation of added acrylonitrile. Thermodynamic parameters like ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are evaluated. Linearity of Exner's plot and constancy in ΔG^\ddagger values suggest operation of a similar type of mechanism in all the ketones. A plausible mechanism rationalising the observed kinetic data is proposed. The rate expression derived from the mechanism is of the form $\text{rate} = k[\text{ketone}]^2[\text{H}^+]^2[\text{NBSac}]^0$. The structural effects are discussed.

THOUGH a number of N-halo compounds have been reported as useful halogenating as well as oxidising agents, very little work has been done^{1,2} on the use of N-bromosaccharin as oxidising or halogenating agent. Further, the mechanism of oxidation of aliphatic, cyclic and arylaliphatic ketones using a variety of oxidants has been the subject of study by several workers^{3–9}, but oxidation or bromination of ketones by the above reagent has not been attempted so far. This prompted us to undertake the title investigation. It has been reported^{1,10} that N–Br bond in N-bromosaccharin is strongly polar and in polar medium it undergoes heterolytic fission to give bromonium ion rather than homolytic cleavage to give bromine free radical. Since this is a prerequisite for allylic bromination this reagent fails to bring about allylic bromination and acts as an oxidising agent only in the case of aliphatic ketones.

Experimental

Acetone, ethyl methyl ketone, isobutyl methyl ketone and acetic acid used were of B.D.H., AR grade. Cyclopentanone, cycloheptanone and *n*-propyl methyl ketone were E. Merck products. All the substrates were purified by distillation before use. Mercuric acetate (Sarabhai Chemicals) and sulphuric acid and potassium iodide (B.D.H., AR) were used as such. N-bromosaccharin (N-BSac) was prepared¹ by brominating saccharin.

All the experiments were conducted under the conditions using tenfold excess of ketone concentration over oxidant concentration. The reactions were initiated by adding the required volume of ketone solution to a mixture of the oxidant, mercuric acetate and sulphuric acid. The kinetics were monitored by estimating the unreacted oxidant iodometrically from time to time. The reactions were studied in the temperature range of 10–50° in 10 to 90% (v/v)

aqueous acetic acid medium in presence of 0.05 to 0.8 M sulphuric acid. Mercuric acetate was used to remove Br[–] which would otherwise produce Br₂ due to reaction with the oxidant.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data obtained at various [N-BSac] fit into zero order rate expression. The zero order rate constants were computed from the plots of [N-BSac] vs time. The rate constants are reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. These rate constants are independent of [N-BSac] suggesting zero order nature of the reaction with respect to [N-BSac]. Such zero order dependence on oxidant concentration is observed in the oxidation of ketones by KBrO₃, NBS⁹, Ti(III)¹¹ and PIA¹².

The effect of [ketone] on the rate of oxidation was studied in the concentration range 0.01 to 0.08 M and the rate constants are evaluated from the zero order plots (Table 1). A linear increase in the rate constants assumes the order of the reaction with respect to ketone as unity. In order to study the effect of [H⁺] on rate of reaction, experiments

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [KETONE] ON OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS IN THE OXIDATION OF KETONES BY N-BROMOSACCHARIN

[N-BSac] = 0.002 M; Hg(OAc)₂ = 0.004 M;
Aq. HOAc = 20% (v/v); [H₂SO₄] = 0.1 M; Temp. = 35°

Ketone	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^7 \text{ M sec}^{-1} \text{ at } [\text{ketone}] \times 10^3 \text{ M}$					
	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	6.0	8.0
Acetone	1.19	2.30	3.39	3.92	6.67	9.01
Ethyl methyl ketone	1.17	2.38	3.47	4.94	6.61	9.12
<i>n</i> -Propyl methyl ketone	1.28	2.57	3.85	5.14	7.78	10.00
Isobutyl methyl ketone	—	1.74	2.69	3.50	5.34	8.00
Cyclopentanone	2.56	5.13	7.59	10.42	15.58	19.61
Cyclohexanone	7.94	16.26	22.22	37.04	50.21	—
Cycloheptanone	1.41	3.03	4.47	5.96	9.26	—

were conducted in the range 0.01 to 0.1 M sulphuric acid, and the zero order rate constants were computed (Table 2). The plots of log k_{obs} against log $[H^+]$ are linear with unit slopes with all the ketones

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [ACID] ON OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS IN THE OXIDATION OF KETONES BY N-BROMOSACCHARIN

[Ketone]=0.02 M; [N-BSac]=0.002 M; [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.004 M; Aq. HOAc=20% (v/v); Temp.=35°

Ketone	$k_{obs} \times 10^7$ M sec ⁻¹ at $[H_2SO_4] \times 10^2$ M					
	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0
Acetone	—	2.30	4.17	8.24	11.91	16.67
Ethyl methyl ketone	1.25	2.38	4.67	9.17	14.17	20.00
Isobutyl methyl ketone	0.92	1.74	3.32	9.20	11.67	15.00
Cyclohexanone*	2.29	5.21	7.41	16.67	25.64	37.04
Cycloheptanone	1.67	3.03	5.56	11.50	19.85	23.82

*Temp.=20°

indicating that the order dependence of rate on $[H^+]$ is unity. Such a behaviour was earlier observed by Venkatasubramanian *et al*¹⁸ who postulated the rate determining enolisation as an important step. Study of the reaction using acetic acid-water mixtures of different proportions shows (Table 3) that there was increase in the rate with increase in acetic acid content of the solvent. This may be attributed to a lowering of the dielectric constant of the medium which favours reactions involving protonation¹⁴. Further, the plot of log k_{obs} vs reciprocal of the

dielectric constant was linear with positive slope for different ketones. This observation suggests a positive ion-dipole type of reaction in accordance with Amis treatment of rate data¹⁵ with respect to dielectric constant of the medium. From the slopes of the Amis plots the distance of closest approach calculated come out to be 1.9 Å which is of the reasonable order of magnitude for an ion-dipole reaction. The ion-dipole nature of the reaction was further confirmed by studying the effect of salts on rate of reaction. The added salts did not vary the rates. The rate constants were unaffected at different concentrations of added saccharin and mercuric acetate. Such a behaviour has been earlier observed by Venkatasubramanian *et al*⁹ in the oxidation of cyclohexanone by N-bromosuccinimide.

In order to evaluate the activation parameters experiments were carried in the temperature range of 10 to 50° and the zero order rate constants were evaluated. The activation parameters were evaluated by plotting log k vs 1/T and the observed rate data are given in Table 4. The nearly same free energy of activation of the order of 118 kJ mol⁻¹ suggests probably the similar type of mechanism is operative in the oxidation of all the ketones studied. This is further supported by the linearity of Exner's plot¹⁶ of log k_{obs} (at 30°) vs log k_{obs} (at 50°). The value of the isokinetic temperature, β , obtained from the slope of the above plot is less than the reaction temperature (303-323 K) indicating that the reaction

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS IN THE OXIDATION OF KETONES BY N-BROMOSACCHARIN

[Ketone]=0.02 M; [N-BSac]=0.002 M; [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.004 M; [H₂SO₄]=0.1 M; Temp.=35°

Ketone	$k_{obs} \times 10^7$ M sec ⁻¹ at % HOAc (v/v)									
	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	
Acetone	—	2.30	2.38	2.38	2.78	3.03	3.71	4.90	7.94	
Ethyl methyl ketone	—	2.38	2.38	2.57	2.67	3.03	3.51	5.18	—	
Isobutyl methyl ketone	—	1.74	1.85	2.09	2.22	2.38	2.78	3.50	6.06	
Cyclopentanone	4.76	5.13	5.54	5.54	6.06	6.67	7.88	10.45	18.52	
Cyclohexanone	16.26	16.26	15.16	16.26	16.21	—	22.22	37.04	—	
Cycloheptanone	3.18	3.03	3.18	2.90	3.28	3.50	4.44	5.78	10.42	

TABLE 4—ORDER OF REACTIVITY AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS IN THE OXIDATION OF KETONES BY N-BROMOSACCHARIN

[Ketone]=0.02 M; [N-BSac]=0.002 M; [H₂SO₄]=0.1 M; [Hg(OAc)₂]=0.004 M; Aq. HOAc=20% (v/v); Temp.=30°

Ketone	$k_{obs} \times 10^7$ M sec ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mole ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mole ⁻¹
Acetone	2.30	74.1 (72.8)	146.0 (144.4)	119.0 (114.7)
Ethyl methyl ketone	2.38	66.4 (69.4)	171.0 (146.8)	119.0 (114.6)
n-Propyl methyl ketone	2.57	74.1 (73.8)	137.0 (132.9)	114.6 (114.4)
Isobutyl methyl ketone	1.74	74.1 (72.8)	149.0 (138.3)	118.3 (115.5)
Cyclopentanone	5.13	69.3 (70.5)	166.0 (137.1)	120.5 (112.7)
Cyclohexanone	16.26	67.0 (68.1)	146.0 (135.3)	112.2 (109.8)
Cycloheptanone	3.03	72.1 (70.1)	154.0 (142.8)	119.6 (114.1)

* The values given in paranthesis are evaluated by the linear least square method. The values coincide with each other within ±4% error.

is entropy controlled which is evident from the data in Table 4.

The reaction system did not induce polymerisation of added acrylonitrile confirming that there are no free radicals in the system. Stoichiometric investigation showed that one mole of ketone consumes two mole of N-bromosaccharin giving rise to the respective diketone. Hence the corresponding stoichiometric equation can be written as :

Product analysis confirmed that the corresponding diketones were the products. Pyruvaldehyde was identified in the case of acetone. The diketones were characterised by the formation of corresponding coloured inner complex nickel dioxime salts¹⁷ and by corresponding 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrozones.

On the basis of the above kinetic data and taking into consideration the contention of Littler and Waters¹⁸ that two electron oxidants attack enol form rather than keto form, the rate controlling step in the present oxidation has been written as the enolisation of the corresponding ketone. A parallel study with bromine which shows that the oxidation rate with N-bromosaccharin and bromination proceed with the same rate supports the above view. The oxidation and bromination rate constants in the case of acetone and cyclohexanone are 2.30×10^{-7} and 2.27×10^{-7} , and 16.26×10^{-7} and $16.42 \times 10^{-7} M \text{ sec}^{-1}$, respectively. Hence the first and rate controlling step of the oxidation is

The subsequent step involves a fast electron transfer to the oxidant ultimately giving rise to the diketone showing the independent nature of the reaction with respect to oxidant. The probable mechanism can be envisaged as shown in Scheme 1.

From the mechanism given a rate expression is derived of the form

$$-d[\text{N}-\text{BSac}]/dt = k [\text{ketone}]^1 [\text{H}^+]^1$$

which shows the first order nature of the reaction with respect to both ketone and hydrogen ion, and zero order dependence with respect to oxidant.

A perusal of rate data presented in Table 4 shows that under similar experimental conditions, the order of reactivity among aliphatic ketones is *n*-propyl methyl ketone > ethyl methyl ketone > acetone > isobutyl methyl ketone. With an exception of isobutyl

where R = H, CH₃, C₂H₅, C₃H₇

Scheme 1

methyl ketone the order of reactivity is in consonance with the enol stability of the corresponding ketones. The lower reactivity of isobutyl methyl ketone can be attributed to steric factor. In the molecular model constructed, the distance between the methyl and -OH is less than the sum of the van der Waals radii resulting in repulsive interactions. Such an observation was earlier reported by Radhakrishnamurthy *et al*⁹. The reactivity pattern obtained in the case of cyclic ketones is C₆ > C₅ > C₇ which is again in the order of their enol content^{5,16-21}. The higher reactivity of cyclohexanone is due to the terminal hydrogen of the nearly strainless puckered residue (CH₂)₄ in cyclohexene fulfilling the stereochemical requirement for hyper-conjugation with the cyclic C=C group better than does the terminal hydrogen of the nearly flat residue (CH₂)₃ in cyclopentanone²². This also explains the higher enol content of cyclohexanone. It is generally presumed that the most favoured conformation of cycloheptanone is the twist chair form which is responsible for the lesser enol content and consequently to lower rate.

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